

What do we really know about Brasilia? Misleading and prejudice in canonical books

The purpose of this paper is to draw attention to the way that Brasilia has been described in canonical architecture books, read and studied all over the world. We believe that, through a series of misleading information and prejudiced interpretation, Brasilia, in the last decades, has not received the appropriate approach it deserves. On the contrary, the critics disdained Brasilia when they should consider it one of the greatest achievements of the modern movement. This work does not aim to be a deep analysis of the architectural historiography of Brasilia, but to suggest that critics should consider this capital city, four decades after its completion, as a lively, strong evolving city and not as a photograph of the past.

Brasilia became known to the world not as an urban plan, but mainly as a set of architectural still photographs, showing isolated governmental buildings in the middle of the dust, taken while the city was under construction. These images were repeated over and over through articles and magazines, and were reproduced almost the same way in the canonical architectural handbooks, that transmitted them through generations of architecture students. Those frozen images of the past were seemingly used as utterly information for the authors' understanding about the landscape, the urban plan and the architecture, interpreted as of desolated and oppressive appearance. This "traditional" set of pictures were taken as the image of Brasilia in its totality, when they were just showing one of its particular aspect, even if a very important one, namely the

governmental buildings Niemeyer conceived with a proper and necessary monumental character. They seem not to distinguish between Lucio Costa's urban plan and Niemeyer's buildings: this very important fact is not at all dealt in the canonical books. Besides that, the only aspects most authors emphasize about Brasilia are the novel forms and visual drama of Niemeyer's buildings. The urban design is generally briefly mentioned as a "two wing" or "cross" form, with no consistent references to the urban concepts that guided the design of one of the greatest "Modern Cities" of the world.

Nevertheless, in the meanwhile the vegetation was growing, the buildings were being completed, people were living their daily life and Brasilia was gaining reality in spite of its initial crudeness. However, even later critics, writing in the 80's, retained those primeval images of an uncompleted city, and apparently made no other efforts to verify its reality, or its possible change. It is interesting to note how prejudice and misleading were transmitted from a canonical book to another, almost untouched, which let one imagine the extension of the damage a wrong approach may cause.

In order to exemplify that, let us call attention to a passage in Tafuri's and dal Co's *Storia dell'architettura. Architettura Contemporanea II* (1979), precisely, at the Chapter XVII, written by Tafuri (Tafuri, 1979:337)

"...born from demagogic intentions, in the middle of the jungle, is guided by a childish allegoric plan, that tries to reinterpret an urban model already experimented in Soviet Union in the 30's"

That's all he says about Brasilia's urban design, referring to it as "childish" and "allegoric", and giving the reader the impression that it is not serious or worth any kind of description or analysis. When he locates the city "in the middle of the jungle", it seems to be clear that the affirmation is tainted with the stereotypical image of Brazil as a tropical country covered by an uninterrupted jungle. Well, this represents a geographical mistake in two aspects. First one, in Brazil we have rain forests, not jungles; second one, the Amazon Forest is thousands of miles away from Brasilia.

And he continues:

"Niemeyer showed the limitations of his poetic, that became a common maniera repeated to nausea [...] with spectacular, but superfluous fancy." (Tafuri, 1979: 323)

Maybe he is right but this do not alter the fact that no consistent reasons are presented to justify this opinion. At least not like Leonardo Benevolo, in his

1960's *Storia dell'architettura moderna*, nineteen years before did:

"As Haussman in his time, Costa and Niemeyer proposed themselves the creation of a new urban landscape, experimenting already acquired compositional formulas in a new scale. Although the critiques we make today to Brasília are very similar to those made to Haussman's Paris one century ago, emphasising the artfulness and the abstraction of the adopted instruments without valuing the methodological importance of his usage in new circumstances and its thoughts, be then problematic or not, that derives from the future city design systems.

If we can judge Brasilia's architecture in a severe way, but in its real own terms, it will be as a new urban space which takes this form. Because the Brasilia's experiment employs the modern urban culture and anticipates, in various aspects, the development possibilities." (Benevolo, 1966:1026)

Benevolo's book, written soon after the inauguration, shows a balanced position, and suggests that Brasília, even when judged in a severe way, should be taken in its own terms. Unfortunately, this is not what happened with other "canonical", which includes Tafuri's, that appeared de following decades. When we take Kenneth Frampton's *Modern Architecture: a Critical History* (1980), we are led to deduce that his vision is influenced by Tafuri's, be by the position of his interpretation, be by the presence of the same geographical mistake, as follows:

"... soon after its foundation, Brasilia emerged as two cities: the monumental city of government and big business to which the bureaucrats commuted by air from Rio, on the 'shanty town', or favela, whose inhabitants served the 'radiance' of the high city."
"... his work (Niemeyer's) at Brasilia which, together with Costa's grid, evoked the aura of the genre terrible, the assertion of implacable form against remorseless nature; for beyond the order of Brasilia's Capitol, edged by an artificial lake, there lay the infinite extent of the jungle (1980)." (Frampton, 1980:256)

Frampton refers to the town right after its foundation. And what about a decade later, or say two, when the text was written? Not even a word about, even in the revised edition, of 1997, where the term "jungle" was replaced by "savannah" (Frampton, 1997:256), which is the African correspondence for what we call "cerrado".

The term jungle started to haunt Brasilia's landscape in August, 1958, in the American Architec-

tural Magazine *Architectural Forum*, in a note: *Brazil's Jungle Capital*

"One of the most ambitious, start-from-scratch building projects of all time is Brazil's building of a new capital city in the midst of a **desolate jungle** area some 600 miles north of Rio de Janeiro. Brasilia, as the city will be called, was the dream of Brazilian President Juscelino Kubitschek, and last month he saw the beginning of his dream coming true. The first two major buildings of the new city were opened: the President's own place, called the Palace of Dawn, and a glass-walled 135-room hotel. A small chapel was also completed recently. Under construction are apartments, government ministry buildings and other buildings. Brasília, which in ten years is expected to be a city of 500,000 persons, will cost at least \$70 million, probably eventually nearly \$ 1 billion, including private investment. The overall plan for the city was by Architect Lucio Costa. The major government buildings in Brasilia were designed by Architect Oscar Niemeyer, who will move his own office there soon. The white marble, glass and aluminium palace is called "Oscar's cardiogram" because of the jagged line of reinforced concrete pylons that guard the entrance." (*'Brazil's Jungle Capital'*, 1958: 13)

Back to Frampton, his text may lead the reader to imagine that there are no middle classes in this city, only bureaucrats and the shanty towns inhabitants interact. So we have no clue what the 'super-cuadras' (with a "c") that he mentions in his text, are all about. (Frampton, 1980:256)

About Niemeyer's designs, it hardly could be interpreted as an assertion of implacable forms against remorseless nature, but rather an attempt to give monumental character to governmental buildings. [He clearly states that in his testimony of February 1958, not mentioning a word about the remorseless nature or even a possible return to Classical absolutes].

Finally, when we examine William Curtis' *Modern Architecture Since 1900* (1982), we find again an emphasis on Niemeyer's forms and only a minimal comment about Lucio Costa's plan:

"Oscar Niemeyer's State buildings at Brasilia, built in the late 1950s drew more on the example of the pre-war Le Corbusier, or on the model of Harrison's and Abramovitz version of the U.N. than on the style of the late works. As at Chandigarh a new urban form had to be conceived on a virgin site, Lucio Costa, the architect of the overall plan, designed wings spreading out in a slight arc from the focal point. The president's palace and main

congress buildings were laid out in front of vast piazzas with water and sky becoming essential elements of the composition. But Niemeyer's buildings lacked the force of those at Chandigarh. The president's palace, for example, had a mannered façade of smoothly finished inverted arches. The main chambers of the congress were expressed by saucer-shaped elements – one face down, the other face up – alongside the dominating element of the secretariat slab. It is possible that this imagery satisfied the technocratic aspirations and a thirst for grandeur on the part of the Brazilian élite: but the forms were inflated, diagrammatic and lacking in symbolic or sculptural substance." (Curtis, 1982:307)

Here, the wide spaces around the president's palace and the congress are understood as "vast piazzas". But the aim, in this case, was not to create an urban space with the function of a piazza, a square, but to accentuate the monumental character of the buildings.

Curtis uses the same concept that Tafuri and Dal Co: here a "mannered façade", there, a "common maniera", to criticise in a negative way the expression of the governmental buildings. In addition to this, when talking about Brasília, Tafuri and Dal Co employ terms such as "childish", "allegoric", "nausea" and "superfluous"; Curtis uses "saucer-shaped", "inflated" and "lacking in symbolic or sculptural substance". In both cases, the reader may feel that there are too few lines of real analysis for so many adjectives.

The same proportion of adjectives can not be found in two works written specifically about Brasília: Norma Evenson's "Two Brazilian Capitals: Architecture and Urbanism in Rio de Janeiro and Brasília" (1973), and James Holston's, an American anthropologist, "The Modern City" (1993). Both books follow Leonardo Benevolo's proposition that Brasília should be understood in its own terms. It is important to observe that both works are result from rigorous academic researches, and do not have the same widespread dissemination of the canonical books. But their existence reinforces the idea that, in order to make a critical assessment of the architecture of Brasília, it is necessary to restore the facts and deepen the analysis, opening the debate on a clearer basis.

We hope that the next canonical books will offer us, and all over the world, a fairer critical view of what Brasília really represents in the Brazilian and the International architectural context.

Fig. 1 – Brasília Air View.

Fig. 2 – Brasília. "Super quadra".

Fig.3 – Brasília. Monumental Axis.

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